

Synthesis of Substituted Ureas: Some α -Benzamido Cinnamo Phenyl Ureas

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With a view to synthesising a few substituted ureas required for some other purpose, vanillin and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde have been condensed with hippuric acid in presence of acetic anhydride and anhydrous sodium acetate to yield 2-phenyl-4-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzylidene)-(Ia) and 2-phenyl-(*p*-hydroxy benzylidene)-5-oxazolones¹ (Ib). These on treatment with hydrazine hydrate in ethereal solution are converted into the corresponding hydrazides² (II), which, on treatment with nitrous acid, furnish azides³ (III).

a : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$; $R_4 = -OH$; $R_5 = -OCH_3$

b : $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = H$; $R_5 = OH$

1. Bergel et al., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 261.

2. Vanghelovici and Stefanescu, *Chem. Abs.*, 1944, 38, 5300.

3. Jensen and Howland, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 1988.

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The azides undergo Curtius rearrangement in hot benzene to provide oxadiazines⁴ (IV). Direct heating with aromatic amines in inert solvents furnish substituted ureas⁵ (V). Substituted ureas obtained from α -benzamido-4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamoyl azide (IIIa) have been reported in Table I, and those from α -benzamido-4-hydroxycinnamoyl azide (IIIb) in Table II.

TABLE I

 α -Benzamido-4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamo-substituted phenylureas

S. No.	Aniline used	Substituted phenyl ureas	Formula	*M.P.	Colour	%Nitrogen Found Reqd.	
1	4-Bromo-A	4'-Bromo-P	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₃ Br	225°	Sepia	8.27	8.71
2	4-Chloro-A	4'-Chloro-P	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	220	Lemon yellow	9.19	9.60
3	2:4-Dichloro-A	2':4'-Dichloro-P	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂	247	„	8.43	8.89
4	2:5-Dichloro-A	2':5'-Dichloro-P	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂	227	Dull yellow	8.32	8.89
5	3-Chloro-4-bromo-A	3'-Chloro-4' bromo-P	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ BrCl	245	Dirty yellow	7.79	8.13
6	2-Methyl-A	2'-Methyl-P	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃	100	Brown	9.68	10.07
7	3-Methyl-A	3'-Methyl-P	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃	120	„	9.59	10.07
8	4-Methyl-A	4'-Methyl-P	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃	100	Dirty yellow	9.71	10.07
9	2:4-Dimethyl-A	2':4'-Dimethyl-P	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₃	105	Dark tan	9.42	9.74
10	3-Nitro-A	3'-Nitro-P	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₄	233	Dull yellow	11.88	12.28
11	4-Nitro-A	4'-Nitro-P	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₄	245	Yellow	11.84	12.28
12	2-Bromo-4-ethoxy-A	2'-Bromo-4' ethoxy-P	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₃ Br	241	Light brown	7.58	7.98
13	4-Ethoxy-A	4'-Ethoxy-P	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₃	102	Dark brown	8.98	9.39

N.B.—A denotes Aniline and P, Phenyl.

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

2-Phenyl-4-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-5-oxazolone (Ia).—A mixture of vanillin (3 g.), fused sodium acetate (1.0 g.), hippuric acid (3.0 g.) and acetic anhydride (6 ml.) were heated on a water bath, till it set to a yellow mass. It was then treated with water (100 ml.), cooled, filtered, and washed with hot water followed by cold ethanol. The product was crystallised from ethanol in bright yellow needles, m.p. 191°, yield 5 g. (84%). (Found: N, 4.34. C₁₇H₁₃O₄N requires N, 4.74%).

Similarly, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (3 g.), when condensed with hippuric acid (4 g.), provided yellow shining needles of 2-phenyl-4-(*p*-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-oxazolone (Ib) 5 g. (78%), m.p. 173°. (Found: N, 4.91. C₁₆H₁₁O₃N requires N, 5.28%).

α -Benzamido-4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamohydrazone (IIa).—The preceding oxazolone (Ia) (5 g.), was treated with a solution of 85% hydrazine hydrate (4 ml.) in ether (40 ml.) with stirring. The yellow colour of the oxazolone was immediately discharged. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (4 g., 72%), m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 12.53. C₁₇H₁₇O₄N₃ requires N, 12.84%).

4. Jennings, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1512.

5. Jones and Mason, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2528; Sah and Ma, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 2, 159.

Similarly, 2-phenyl-4-(*p*-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-oxazolone (Ib) (5 g.) with hydrazine hydrate (4 ml.) in ether furnished colorless needles of α -benzamido-*p*-hydroxy cinnamohydrazide (IIb), 3.8 g. (68%), m.p. 218°. (Found: N, 13.82. $C_{16}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14.14%).

α -Benzamido-4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamoyl Azide (IIIa).—A solution of the preceding hydrazide (IIA) (3 g.) dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml.), was treated with a solution of sodium nitrite (1 g.) in water (5 ml.) with constant stirring. The temperature was maintained below 10°. The yellow precipitate separating was filtered, washed with water and dried; yield 2.8 g. (90%); it decomposed without melting at 225°. (Found: N, 16.31. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_4$ requires N, 16.56%).

Similarly, α -benzamido-*p*-hydroxycinnamohydrazide (3 g.) furnished yellow crystals of α -benzamido-*p*-hydroxycinnamoyl azide (IIIb), 2.6 g. (84%), m.p. 137° (decomp.). (Found: N, 17.85. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_4$ requires N 18.18%).

α -Benzamido-4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamophenylurea (Va).—A mixture of the azide (IIIa) (1 g.) and aniline (5 ml.) was heated on a water bath till the evolution of nitrogen had ceased. On acidification (dil. HCl) of the product formed yellow mass obtained was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles (80%), m.p. 198°. (Found: N, 10.21. $C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_3$, $C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_3$ requires N, 10.42%). Other α -benzamido-4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamophenylureas, similarly prepared are recorded in Table I.

Similarly ureas, obtained by the condensation of α -benzamido-*p*-hydroxy cinnamoyl azide and aniline, are recorded in Table II. These are obtained in well crystalline and good yields ranging from 65-85%.

TABLE II
 α -Benzamido-4-hydroxy cinnamo-substituted phenylureas

S. No.	Aniline used	Substituted phenyl ureas	Formula	*M.P.	Colour	%Nitrogen	
						Found	Reqd.
1	Aniline	Phenyl	$C_{20}H_{19}O_3N_3$	240°	White	10.98	11.26
2	4-Bromo-A	4'-Bromo-P	$C_{22}H_{19}O_3N_3Br$	215	Dirty white	8.96	9.29
3	4-Chloro-A	4'-Chloro-P	$C_{20}H_{18}O_3N_3Cl$	180	Light yellow	9.89	10.30
4	2:4-Dichloro-A	2':4'-Dichloro-P	$C_{22}H_{17}O_3N_3Cl_2$	135	Dirty yellow	9.12	9.50
5	2:5-Dichloro-A	2':5'-Dichloro-P	$C_{22}H_{17}O_3N_3Cl_2$	140	Light brown	9.18	9.50
6	3-Chloro-4-bromo-A	3'-Chloro-4'-bromo-P	$C_{22}H_{17}O_3N_3BrCl$	206	,,	8.98	8.63
7	2-Methyl-A	2'-Methyl-P	$C_{23}H_{21}O_3N_3$	108	Brownish black	10.56	10.85
8	3-Methyl-A	3'-Methyl-P	$C_{23}H_{21}O_3N_3$	246	White	10.61	10.85
9	4-Methyl-A	4'-Methyl-P	$C_{23}H_{21}O_3N_3$	213	Sepia	10.57	10.85
10	2:4-Dimethyl-A	2':4'-Dimethyl-P	$C_{25}H_{23}O_3N_3$	104	Dark tan	10.11	10.47
11	3-Nitro-A	3'-Nitro-P	$C_{20}H_{18}O_5N_4$	140	Dark cream	12.98	13.39
12	4-Nitro-A	4'-Nitro-P	$C_{20}H_{18}O_5N_4$	187	Pale yellow	12.86	13.39
13	4-Ethoxy-A	4'-Ethoxy-P	$C_{24}H_{23}O_4N_3$	120	Brownish black	9.89	10.07
14	3-Chloro-2-methyl-A	5'-Chloro-2'-methyl-P	$C_{23}H_{20}O_3N_3Cl$	Above 315	Cream yellow	9.62	9.96

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3,4-Dihydro-6-phenyl-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxy)-benzylidene-2-oxo-1,3,5-oxadiazine(IVa).
—The azide (IIIa) (2 g.) in benzene (20 ml.) was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The filtered solution on cooling furnished shining orange needles of the product(IVa); yield 1.5 g. (83%), m.p. 240°. (Found: N, 8.58. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 9.03%).

Similarly, α -benzamido-*p*-hydroxycinnamoyl Azide (2 g.), with benzene provided lemon-yellow needles of 3,4-dihydro-6-phenyl-*p*-hydroxybenzylidene-2-oxo-1,3,5-oxadiazine (IVb), yield 1.6 g. (80%), m.p. 130°. (Found: N, 9.75. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.00%).

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